

Original Research Article

Parents' Knowledge about Bronchial Asthma towards Bronchopneumonia Children at the University of Lahore Teaching Hospital, Pakistan

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Abstract

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Bronchopneumonia is a type of pneumonitis that causes infection in the Bronchioles. Somebody with bronchopneumonia may have distress inhalation since their airlines are restrained. Due to infection, their lungs may not contract adequate air. The objective of this study was to assess the knowledge regarding bronchial asthma towards bronchopneumonia children among parents in the University of Lahore Teaching Hospital. A quantitative descriptive cross sectional study design was used for this study to identify the attitude and belief of parents regarding experience of bronchial asthma. The site is the overall location for the research. The study site was The University of Lahore teaching hospital. A quantitative descriptive cross sectional study of 150 caregivers of bronchial asthma towards bronchopneumonia children were used for this study to identify the attitude and belief of parents regarding experience of bronchial asthma. Parents of asthmatic children of average age of 4-7 years and above visited the physician with their child Outpatient Department (OPD) of pediatrics, the University of Lahore teaching hospital. In this study, 56% of children were boys and 44% were girls. The average age was 1-3y (Mean $\pm$ S.D = 1.72 $\pm$ 0.778). The average period for living through bronchial asthma illness was 1 month (Mean $\pm$ S.D = 1.82 $\pm$ 0.795). 39.3% of members did not have knowledge about the inhaled corticosteroids and also 48% members did not know what way it functions. Although 66% had awareness about aerosol treatment. Parents who had ever used children's asthma control questionnaire was (n=57) 38% and that parents who had written any type of action plan for providing care during asthma exacerbation was (n=63) 42%. There is a vital requirement for the planning of parent strategies to avoid bronchial asthma illness, also its squeal.

Keywords: Allergic substance, Asthma, Bronchial asthma, Bronchopneumonia, Parent's attitude, Parents knowledge, Respiratory health

INTRODUCTION

Bronchopneumonia is a type of pneumonitis that causes infection in the Bronchioles. Somebody with broncho-pneumonia may have distress inhalation since their airlines are restrained. Due to infection, their lungs may not contract adequate air. Indications of broncho-pneumonia can be minor or plain. Experimental signs of

bronchial asthma are controlled by proper use of medication. This depends on when signs and symptoms appear then treatment should be done to avoid serious attacks of bronchial asthma. There should be a relation between doctor and patient to explore and decrease experience of the risk factor before assessment,

treatment, and prevention of bronchial asthmatic attack. Therefore information about bronchial asthma as well as its risk factors and causes and the assertiveness to the managing and the consumption of bronchodilators is crucial. Although the accessibility of simple and active treatments, the proportions of children testified to have bronchial asthma indications is high in Sudan, as well as 12% of children's suffering from bronchial asthma in Khartoum. The goals of the study were to evaluate the knowledge of the caregiver and to classify their assertiveness and practices toward their children's (National Institutes of Health, 2006).

Medical specialists are qualified to accomplish bronchial asthma exacerbations in hospital-based surroundings. Though, the fundamental ecological activities by no adherence to therapeutic instruction are main tasks in avoiding exacerbations.

Rendering to the WHO worldwide well-being estimations, the entire quantity of expiries happening 2011 was documented to be 54,591,414, and non-communicable illnesses added to 66% of the whole expiries. The harshness of bronchial asthma is observable over its influence to 3, 74, 678 expiries happening 2011. Bronchopneumonia is a most communal chronic illness, interpretations for approximately 300 million persons obtainable of the entire inhabitants. Bronchial Asthma incidence happening to children remains cumulatively universal (Noureddin et al., 2019)

Description of bronchial asthma harshness, such as revised in the Global Alliance beside Chronic Lung disease, describes severe asthma as "Unrestrained bronchial asthma which has consequence in risk of everyday deaths and/or antagonistic response to medicine and/or chronic illness (as well as decreased respiratory function and compact lobe of lung development in offspring)". Amongst children, 13-14 years age group, the worldwide average intended for present cough existed 14.1% also in Indian sub-continent documented an occurrence <5% (Salvador Jr, 2012).

Worldwide prevalence for present respiratory infection originated may be 11.5% of the 6-7 years age group; Indian subcontinent had a dominance of 6.8%. Inside 13-14 years of age group 6.9% chronic respiratory infection indications worldwide as well as the Indian subcontinent displayed lowermost prevalence 2.5% between entirely the education settings. 6-7 years of age group children had 4.9% indications of severe bronchial asthma global, although 2.5% the Indian subcontinent had an occurrence. A major chronic illness is identified as bronchial asthma, it is very vital to inform and manage the overall people. A study connecting the caregiver of bronchial asthmatic children in Chennai presented only 3% of the example people recognized accurately what bronchial asthma was, viewing deprived knowledge

between mothers. (Zhao et al., 2010).

These consequences remained comparable to after a study accompanied in Chandigarh in 1995, which had deficiency of information overcome between caregivers. In the study of Ashutoshlai, 34% of the caregivers believe that bronchial asthma is an infectious disease as well as 48% were uncertain for mentioning their children as bronchial asthma (National Institutes of Health, 1995).

The deficiency of awareness in parents about their children that are suffering from bronchial asthma showed that it's not only in India however also worldwide. A study in China as well as its 29 provinces presented that only 18% of parents had information of bronchial asthma. The objective of this study was to assess the knowledge of bronchial asthma among the parents of asthmatic children and to comprehend parents' attitude and practices in dealing with their children's asthma exacerbation (Salvador Jr., 2012).

A study connecting the caregiver of bronchial asthmatic children in Chennai presented only 3% of the examples people recognized accurately what bronchial asthma was, viewing deprived knowledge between mothers. These consequences remained comparable to after a study accompanied in Chandigarh in 1995, which had deficiency of information overcome between caregivers. In the study of Ashutoshlai, 34% of the caregivers believe that bronchial asthma is infectious disease as well as 48% were uncertain for mentioning their children as bronchial asthma (Klett-Tammen, et al., 2015)

Research question

- What is the parent's knowledge about bronchial asthma towards bronchopneumonia children's?
- What are the current practices of parents regarding bronchial asthma towards bronchopneumonia children's?

Significance

The study will enhance the knowledge of parents about bronchial asthma towards bronchopneumonia children's. Moreover, the study will help the parents to overcome their weakness and boost up the strong point, as a result quality of child care will be improved as well as health and morale of the parents will be enhanced. The results will be shared to the institutional authorities that help them to modify the new standards and policies. Better quality of parents care and practices will lead to enhance the organizational productivity as well as to generate the knowledge or information for the others.

Purpose of the study

Is to explore knowledge and practices of prevalence of bronchial asthma towards bronchopneumonia children among parents in the university of Lahore teaching hospital, Pakistan

Research Objectives

To assess the knowledge regarding bronchial asthma towards bronchopneumonia children among parents of the university of Lahore teaching hospital.

To study the practices of parents toward bronchial asthma about bronchopneumonia children's

Study design

A quantitative descriptive cross sectional study design was used for this study to identify the attitude and belief of parents regarding experience of bronchial asthma. Descriptive research defines what happens and could help to expose original information and significance. The descriptive study is planned to achieve new statistics about individualities in a specific field of studies. (Fox, W. & Bayat, M.S. 2015).

Study Site

The site was the overall location for the research. The study site was The University of Lahore New Campus. This university Established in 1999 by Mr. M A Raof, under the supports of the Ibadan Educational Trust

Study Setting

The university of Lahore teaching Hospital

Target population

Target population was the parents of asthmatic children in the University of Lahore teaching hospital. The total study population is 240 parents approximately and 150 were under study. So the study sample will be the 150 parents.

Sampling Method

A convenient sampling method will be used for this study. It is the easiest and the most convenient method of recruiting the sources of the primary data for research.

Inclusion Criteria

Parents Who were willing to participate and were available during data collection. Parents who will full time participate in study.

Exclusion Criteria

Study excluded parents who refused to participate in the study and who were not available at the time of Data collection.

Data Collection Plan

Data collection plan is one of the main sources to collect data. An adopted questionnaire was used to collect data from the study participants. The permission will be taken from parents. There will be given time and a free hand to complete it and return it.

Research tool

As a well-structured questionnaire with close ended, Likert scale adopted to assess attitude and knowledge and practices of parents of bronchial asthmatic children towards bronchopneumonia. Questionnaire consisted of two parts, the first part explaining the consent form and demographic data of parents in which name, Age, place of residence, occupation educational level, delivery mode and birth mode, and other parts of questionnaire will clarify the questions.

Ethical consideration

Permission was taken from the relevant head of department via authorization letter, as well as from Moral Review Board Committee of The University of Lahore and HOD of Lahore School of Nursing department for conduct study. Permissions were taken from all the members and permitted to the members to take part in the study or refused to participate, members also had the right to mention name or not. Sufficient material of study was provided to members with support of full permission and this may be attained via a permission form assigned to the survey. Privacy will be considered by informing members. The right of members may be secure by Nuremberg Code of Ethics.

Data analysis

Data analysis will be done by SPSS version 21. Statistical computer software for data analysis. The study will be

Table 1. Demographic Data

S#	Question	Response	f (100%)	Mean±S.D
1	caregiver age	18-25 years	81(54%)	1.66±.793
		26- 30 years	39(26%)	
		35-40 years	30(20%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
2	Sex	Male	39(26%)	1.74±. 440
		Female	111(74%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
3	Type of family	Joint	51(34%)	1.82±.686
		Nuclear	75(50%)	
		Extended	24(16%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
4	Household location	Rural	57(38%)	1.66±.554
		Urban	87(58%)	
		Other	6(4%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
5	Marital statuses	Married	132(8%)	1.18±.519
		Divorce	9(6%)	
		Widow	9(6%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
6	education	>primary	36(24%)	2.08±.747
		High school	66(44%)	
		Graduation	48(32%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
7	Total family members	2-4	87(58%)	1.68±.728
		7-9	42(28%)	
		10-12	21(14%)	
		Total	150(100%)	

descriptive study and all the descriptive statistics will be obtained through the SPSS software.

Table 1 shows the demographics frequencies of the members included in the study. Participants' parents age were 18-25y (n=81) 54.0%, age group of 26-30y (n=39) 26.0%, age group of 35-40y (n=30) 20.0% (Mean±S.D=1.66±.793). Female caregiver was more dominant than male. Female caregiver (n=111) 74% and male caregiver was (n=39) 26% (Mean±S.D=1.74±. 440). Most of the families were living (n=57) 38% in rural areas, (n=87) 58% in urban areas, and (n=6) 4% were living in other areas (Mean±S. D=1.66±.554)In this study (n=132) 88% caregivers were married, (n=9) 6% were divorced and (n=9) 6% were widow (Mean±S.D=1.18±.519). Education of the parents (n=36) 24% were >primary, (n=66) 44% were high school and (n=48) 32% were graduated (Mean±S.D=2.08±.747).(n=87) 58% families had 2-4 members, (n=42) 42% families had 7-10 members and (n=21) 14% families had 10-12 members (Mean±S.D=1.68±.728).

Table 2 shows the details of the Condition of children with bronchial asthma and control. This research stated that, (n=84) 56% child was male and (n=66) 44% was female, at the onset of the disease the child's ages was (n=72) 48%, (n=48)32%, (n=30) 20%by an usual time of life of 1 month (Mean±S.D=1.44±.498) also abnormal

period for alive by bronchial asthma illnesses of 3 months (Mean±S.D=1.72±.778). Most of the caregivers described that their kids were hypersensitive to any kind of postponed particles like pollen, soil and inhale the smoke. (54%) participants had no knowledge about eczema and could not confirm their kid had or not (Mean±S.D=1.74±.629). Though, above sixty percent (60%) described a background record of bronchial asthma. Forty two (42%) members stated that their kid had knowledge of an incident of bronchial asthma in the previous one month (Mean±S.D=1.82±.795). bronchial asthmatic history was found in various families. About Bronchial asthmatic illness, 24% child's did not have it within previous 4 months, 34% had in 3 months, 42% had within the previous 1 month, (n=117) 78% parents used preventive measures and (n=33) 22% parents had not using the preventive measures. 32% regularly treat their child by Pediatricians, (n=60) 40% from General physician and (n=42) 28% from Pulmonologist.

The outcomes with admiration to the parent's knowledge about bronchial asthma are shown in table 3. Though, above sixty percent (60%) described a background record of bronchial asthma. Forty two (42%) members stated that their kid had knowledge of an incident of bronchial asthma in the previous one month. In the current revision, (04%) members said that

Table 2. Condition of children with bronchial asthma and control

S#	Question	Response	f (100%)	Mean±S.D
8	child gender	male	84(56%)	1.44±.498
		Female	66(44%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
9	age at onset the disease	1-3y	72(48%)	1.72±.778
		4-7y	48(32%)	
		8-10y	30(20%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
10	allergic substance	Food items (egg, cheese, peanuts, cake)	36(24%)	1.86±.568
		Any particle (dust, pollen, smoke)	99(66%)	
		Pets	15(10%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
11	history of eczema	yes	54(36%)	1.74±.629
		No	81(54%)	
		Not know about the disease	15(10%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
12	family history of asthma	Grandfather	54(36%)	1.86±.751
		Sibling	63(42%)	
		Parents self	33(22%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
13	Last recent asthma exacerbation?	1month	63(42%)	1.82±.795
		3month	51(34%)	
		4month	36(24%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
14	Do you use any preventive measures?	Yes	117(78%)	1.22±.416
		No	33(22%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
15	Who is regularly treating your child for Bronchial asthma?	Pediatricians	48(32%)	1.96±.776
		General physician	60(40%)	
		Pulmonologist	42(28%)	
		Total	150(100%)	

Table 3. Parent's knowledge about bronchial asthma

S#	Question	Response	f (100%)	Mean±S.D
16	What is asthma?	Reversible bronchial Obstruction	51(34%)	1.90±.880
		induced airway inflammatory disease	78(52%)	
		Communicable disease	6(4%)	
		Genetic problem	15(10%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
17	symptoms suggesting asthma condition?	Wheezing>3mnth	49(32.7%)	2.05±.972
		Coughing>4mnth	63(42%)	
		Relief after using the Bronchodilators	20(13.3%)	
		>6 respiratory infection in last 12 months	18(12%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
18	Does chronic cough indicate asthma?	Yes	102(68%)	1.32±.468
		No	48(32%)	
		Total	150(100%)	

Table 3. Continue

19 What according to you is the stimulus of asthma attacks?	Cold stimulation	18(12%)	
	Exposure to allergens	84(56%)	
	Strong emotional changes	6(4%)	
	All of above	42(28%)	
	Total	150(100%)	2.48±1.028
20 What according to you are the symptoms of asthma attacks?	Chest tightness with restricted breathing	51(34%)	
	dry cough after exercise of sleep	51(34%)	
	Repeated strenuous coughing	18(12%)	
	All of above	30(20%)	
	Total	150(100%)	2.18±1.112
21 Do you know about inhaled corticosteroid?	Yes	91(60.7%)	
	No	59(39.3%)	
	Total	150(100%)	1.399±.4990
22 Do you know how inhaled corticosteroid work?	Yes	78(52%)	
	No	72(48%)	
	Total	150(100%)	1.48±.501
23 If yes, how please specify?	No response	63(42%)	
	Reduce inflammation	69(46%)	
	Decrease obstruction	18(12%)	
	Total	150(100%)	1.70±.673
24 Do you know about aerosol therapy?	Yes	99(66%)	
	No	51(34%)	
	Total	150(100%)	1.34±.475

bronchial asthma is a transmissible illness. (24%) caregivers did not know about the stimulus of bronchial asthmatic attack. In past study of India (54%) caregivers were not familiar with the stimulus of bronchial asthmatic attack. (32%) members were conscious that "breathless $\geq$ 3 months, coughing $\geq$ 4 months, respirational contagion $\leq$ 6 in the past year as well as improvement of indications through consuming inhalers' ' remained types of bronchial asthma. 68% caregiver said that chronic cough indicates asthma and (n=48) 32% caregiver said not (Mean±S.D=1.32±.468) that (n=18) 12.0%, (n=84) 56%, (n=6) 4.0% and (n=42) 28% parents said about the stimulus of the asthma attack (Mean±S.D=2.48±1.028). symptoms of asthma attack by parents was (n=51) 34%, (n=51) 34%, (n=18) 12% and (n=30) 20%.60.7% caregivers knows about inhaled corticosteroids and (n=59) 39.3% caregivers not know about the inhaled corticosteroids.The parents who had knowledge about corticosteroid work were (n=63) 42%, no response, (n=69) 46% said that reduce inflammation, and (n=18) 12% said decrease obstruction.66% caregivers had knowledge about aerosol therapy.

The parent's attitudes and opinions about bronchial asthma are shown in Table 4. The parent's show a very confident attitude amongst the caregivers, who answered approximately the bronchial asthma illness of their children's, 32% parents allow their child to play outdoors and (n=102) 68% did not allow it. n=93) 62% parents said

that their child exercised like a normal child and (n=57) 38% said not. 80% parents said that their child did participate in games if their asthma was under control and (n=30) 20% said not. 93.3% parents said that regular medication controls asthma and (n=10) 6.7% said not. (n=128) 85.3 caregivers said that asthmatic medicine had effected their child's normal growth and (n=22) 14.7% said not.38% said that regular medicine affect drug dependency, (n=60) 40% said that regular medicine affects the immune system and(n=33) 22% said that regular medicine harms the child's immune system. 58% heard about asthma from physicians, (n=54) 36% caregivers heard from TV/radio and (n=9) 6% heard from advertisements/books.

Table 5 shows that preventive measures of asthma attack (n=33) 22% caregiver used preventive measures when condition of their child's is minor, (n=81) 54% visit physician regularly, (n=18) 12% avoid smoking and (n=18) 12% use low smoke fuel for cooking. 69.3% parents monitored their child's condition regularly and (n=46) 30.7% said not.58.7% caregiver used peak flow meter for monitoring their child's condition regularly and (n=62) 41.3% did not use the peak flow meter.40% caregivers visited the physician with their child once in a month, ((n=52) 34.7% caregivers visited the physician with their child 2-3 months, (n=13) 8.7% visited their physician with their child 4-6 months and (n=25) 16.7% caregivers visited the physician with their child when

Table 4. Attitude of parents towards bronchial asthma

S#	Question	Response	f (100%)	Mean±S.D
25	Do you allow your child to play Outdoor game?	Yes	48(32%)	1.68±.468
		No	102(68%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
26	Do you think your child with asthma can exercise like a normal child?	Yes	93(62%)	1.38±.487
		No	57(38%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
27	Do you think your child could participate in games if their asthma was under control?	Yes	120(80%)	1.20±.401
		No	30(20%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
28	Can regular medication control asthma attacks?	Yes	140(93.3%)	1.07±.250
		No	10(6.7%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
29	Does the medication for asthma, inhaled corticosteroids, hinder the normal growth of your child?	Yes	128(85.3%)	1.15±.355
		No	22(14.7%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
30	What are the effects of regular medication?	drug dependency	57(38%)	1.84±.760
		Weak immune system	60(40%)	
		Harm to child's immune system	33(22%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
31	From whom did you first hear of asthma?	Physician	87(58%)	1.48±.610
		TV/radio	54(36%)	
		Advertisement/books	9(6%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
		Total	150(100%)	

Table 5. Practices of parents of bronchial asthmatic children

S#	Question	Response	f (100%)	Mean±S.D
32	What examination has your child undergone?	Pulmonary function test	63(42%)	1.86±.941
		Allergens test	60(40%)	
		Skin prick test	12(8%)	
		All	15(10%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
33	What practices do you use as a preventive measure of asthma attack for your child?	Minor condition of child	33(22%)	2.14±.898
		Visit physician on regular basis	81(54%)	
		Avoid smoking	18(12%)	
		Use low smoke fuel for cooking	18(12%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
34	Do you monitor your child's condition regularly?	Yes	104(69.3%)	1.31±.463
		No	46(30.7%)	
35	Will you use a peak flow meter for monitoring conditions?	Total	150(100%)	1.41±.494
		Yes	88(58.7%)	
		No	62(41.3%)	
36	How often do you visit the physician with your child?	Once in a month	60(40%)	2.02±1.077
		2-3 months	52(34.7%)	
		3-4 months	13(8.7%)	
		When asthma attacks is sever	25(16.7%)	
		Total	150(100%)	

Table 5. Continue

37 Do you insist on the use of inhaled corticosteroids by your child to control asthma?	Yes	102(68%)	1.32±.468
	No	48(32%)	
	Total	150(100%)	
38 What type of medication do you follow?	Antibiotics inhaled corticosteroids	84(56%)	1.72±.963
	Asthalin	36(24%)	
	Salbutamol	18(12%)	
	Salmeterol	12(8%)	
	Total	150(100%)	
39 Do you make your child follow the medication regime with utmost priority?	Yes	104(69.3%)	1.31±.463
	No	46(30.7%)	
	Total	150(100%)	

Table 6. Prevention about asthmatic children's

S#	Question	Response	f (100%)	Mean±S.D
40	Have you ever used children's asthma control test questionnaire?	Yes	57(38%)	1.62±.487
		No	93(62%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
41	Do you have written or any type of action plan for providing care during asthma exacerbation?	Yes	63(42%)	1.58±.495
		No	87(58%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
42	Do you avoid your child from tobacco and flus toys?	Yes	129(86%)	1.14±.348
		No	21(14%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
43	Does your child's pillow have a zipped plastic cover for allergies?	Yes	123(82%)	1.18±.385
		No	27(18%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
44	Does your child's mattress have a zipped plastic cover for allergies?	Yes	132(88%)	1.12±.326
		No	18(12%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
45	Do you use a humidifier/vaporizer in your child's bed room?	Yes	102(68%)	1.32±.468
		No	48(32%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
46	Do you have carpeting in your child's bed room?	Yes	117(78%)	1.22±.416
		No	33(22%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
47	Do you have carpeting in your TV room?	Yes	126(84%)	1.16±.368
		No	24(16%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
48	Does your kitchen have a gas stove?	Yes	129(86%)	1.14±.348
		No	21(14%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
49	Do you sometimes use the gas stove to help heat your house?	Yes	135(90%)	1.10±.301
		No	15(10%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
50	Does your child have any problem with cockroaches, rats, mice?	Yes	78(52%)	1.48±.501
		No	72(48%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
51	Do you have any pets?	Yes	57(38%)	1.62±.487
		No	93(62%)	
		Total	150(100%)	
52	Do you smoke?	Yes	39(26%)	1.74±.440
		No	111(74%)	
		Total	150(100%)	

Table 6. Continue

53 Is there any moisture or mildew anywhere in the house on the ceiling, walls, and windows?	Yes	69(46%)	
	No	81(54%)	
	Total	150(100%)	1.54±.500

asthma attacks was sever.(n=102) 68% caregivers insist on the use of inhaled corticosteroids and (n=48) 32% did not insist on the use of inhaled corticosteroids. Medication used by parent when their child's condition was sick (n=84) 56% used Antibiotics inhaled corticosteroids, (n=36) 24% used asthalin, (n=18) 12% used salbutamol and (n=12) 8% used salmeterol. The caregiver that made your child follow the medication regime utmost priority was (n=104) 69.3% and who did not follow the medication regime utmost priority was (n=46) 30.7%.

Table 6 shows that parents who had ever used children's asthma control questionnaire was (n=57) 38% and who did not ever used children's asthma control questionnaire was (n=93) 62%.parents who had written any type of action plan for providing care during asthma exacerbation was (n=63) 42% and who did not was (n=87) 58%.that the parents who avoid their child's from tobacco and flus toys was (n=129) 86% and who did not avoid was (n=21) 14% .that parents who had their child's pillows zipped plastic cover for allergies was (n=123) 82% and who did not use was (n=27) 18%.Parents who had their child's meters zipped plastic cover for allergies was (n=132) 88% and who did not use was (n=18) 12%. Caregivers who used a humidifier/vaporizer in your child's bedroom was (n=102) 68.0% and who didn't use was (n=48) 32%.78% parents used carpet in their child's room and (n=33) 22% had no use of carpet in their child's room. 84% parents used carpet in their TV room and (n=24) 16% had no use of carpet in their TV room.(n=129) 86% parents had a kitchen stove in their home and (n=21) 14% hadn't kitchen stove in their room. 90% of parents used gas stove to heat their home and (n=15) 10% hadn't used a kitchen stove to heat their home. Children's who had problem from cockroaches, rats, mice were (n=78) 52% and who hadn't problem was (n=72) 48%. 38% parents had pets in their home and (n=93) 62% hadn't pets in their home. Parents who smoke was (n=39) 26% and who didn't smoke was (n=111) 74%.46% of homes were moisture or mildew anywhere in the house on the ceiling, walls, and windows and (n=81) 54% was not moisture.

DISCUSSION

Bronchial Asthma may happen at any stage however the situation starts is mostly experiential in kids as well as youngsters. The caregivers of such asthmatic children remain some of the significant influences happening the

inhibition also managing bronchial asthma illness. Acceptable awareness of bronchial asthma managing in a caregiver remains important used for the anticipation of bronchial asthma illness in the kid. Most of the members in this study had qualification level matric and graduation, and participants in this study were both male and female that were employed.(Brown, R. 2015).

Most of the caregivers described that their kids were hypersensitive to any kind of postponed particles like pollen, soil and inhale the smoke. (54%) participants had no knowledge about eczema and could not confirm whether their kid had or not. Though, above sixty percent (60%) described a background record of bronchial asthma. Forty two (42%) members stated that their kid had knowledge of an incident of bronchial asthma in the previous one month. In the current revision, (04%) members said that bronchial asthma is a transmissible illness. In the past study of India had shown that (16%) members said that bronchial asthma is a transmissible illness. (24%) caregivers did not know about the stimulus of bronchial asthmatic attack (Carvalho Coelho et al., 2016).

In past study of India (54%) caregivers were not familiar with the stimulus of bronchial asthmatic attack. 32% members were conscious that "breathless $\geq$ 3 months, coughing $\geq$ 4 months, respirational contagion $\leq$ 6 in the past year as well as improvement of indications through consuming inhalers" remained types of bronchial asthma. A research lead by Zhao, India, and Chennai presented that 6.08% caregivers had knowledge about "breathless $\geq$ 3 months, coughing $\geq$ 4 month, respirational contagion $\leq$ 6 in the past year as well as improvement of indications through consuming inhalers" remained types of bronchial asthma (Sodhi et al., 2013).

Most of the caregivers observed that smoking was one of the causes for bronchial asthma also the Main cause of bronchial asthma in the kids. In this research study 62% parents said that their child exercised like a normal child. In the previous study 23% members said that their child exercised like a normal child. (Merghani et al., 2012).

Consistent observing of the asthmatic eminence of the kid is important in avoiding outbreaks.69% caregivers in this study, monitoring their child's condition regularly and 59% were expanding through peak flow meters. In the previous research in India, Almost 40% members described that they observed their kids' bronchial asthmatic situation 32% were expanding topmost movement stresses (Jayasutha and Saipavan, 2014).

Most of the members stated that they were completely

assured that their kids were following to medicine. This research was accompanied in a hospital setup by a comparatively minor sample size. (Kodouda and Zachariah, 2014).

Additionally, it was planned as a cross-sectional research, creating it problematic to determine the time-based suggestion. Most of the members had information about bronchial asthma and its causes. Though, parents who had ever used children's asthma control questionnaire was (n=57) 38% and that parents who had written any type of action plan for providing care during asthma exacerbation was (n=63) 42%. There is a vital requirement for the planning of parent strategies for avoiding bronchial asthma illness also its squeal (Noureddin et al., 2019).

Limitations

This study was conducted in a very short period of time in a single hospital set up. Many difficulties faced in data collection. Most people refused to participate in the study.

CONCLUSION

There is a vital requirement for the planning of parent strategies for avoiding bronchial asthma illness also its squeal. This research was accompanied in a hospital setup by a comparatively minor sample size. Additionally, it was planned as a cross-sectional research, creating it problematic to determine the time-based suggestion. Most of the members had information about bronchial asthma and its causes. Though, parents who had ever used children's asthma control questionnaire was (n=57) 38% and that parents who had written any type of action plan for providing care during asthma exacerbation was (n=63) 42%.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, I would like to thank Allah Almighty who is king of kings and give me strength, opportunity, knowledge, success and ability to complete this research paper satisfactorily. However, it would not have been possible without the kind support and help of many individuals. I would like to extend my sincere thanks to all of them. I am highly indebted to my supervisor Mr. Muhammad Hussain for their useful comments, encouragement, guidance, and constant supervision as well as for providing necessary information regarding the research work and also for their support in completing the research. I would like to express my gratitude to my HOD, Lahore School of Nursing Mr. Muhammad Afzal

who gave me golden opportunity to conduct this research work. I would like to express my gratitude towards "my strength" my parents for their support and encouragement which helped me in completion of this project. My thanks and appreciations go to my family, friends and colleagues who supported me in all perspectives. I'm also thankful to the management of the University of Lahore.

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